

mHealth Strategy for TB Eradication

Health Innovation Challenge

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I. Topic Selection, Concept, and Vision: **Tuberculosis Eradication**

A. Description of the problem

Tuberculosis (TB) is a disease caused by a *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. It usually affects the lungs.

The mode of transmission of TB is through air droplet released through cough or sneeze from a person with lung TB. After inhalation and though already infected, a person may stay in the latent phase (asymptomatic and non-transmitting) of the disease even for the rest of his/ her life.

TB is a treatable and curable disease.^[1] TB-DOTS is the course of treatment usually prescribed to patients. Under this, four (to five) antimicrobial drugs will be given to patients on a six-month standard period with ongoing support and supervision from trained healthcare providers. Several studies show different percentages of non-compliance on various parts of the globe (18%^[2] and 55%^[3] in two studies we reviewed), but the common contributing factors were inadequate knowledge, social and behavioral factors, and health care facilities and services.

Strict adherence to the aforementioned prescribed course of treatment is pivotal as failure to do so may just lead to the worsening of the patient's prognosis because of high chances of TB bacteria that are still alive may become resistant to those drugs. TB that is resistant to drugs is harder and more expensive to treat.

B. Description of solution components

Directly addressing the specific factors contributing to the problem gives us a firm grasp on what kind of strategy we need to apply to solve it.

Knowledge (About Disease and Treatment)

Experiencing unexpected side effects following medication was found to be a common reason for non-compliance. It is also quite alarming to note that among non-compliant patients, only 20% were aware of the causative agent of TB. Knowledge about the disease and treatment could be further improved through

information campaigns, and, considering a study conducted by Bam et al in 2004-2005 saying that 72% of non-compliant patients are illiterate, explanations should be easier to understand, like by using the local language and colorful pictures whenever applicable.

Behavioral and Social Factors

Hiding and spitting out the medicines is common. TB patients also suffer from social exclusion and discrimination, and that TB is a highly stigmatized disease. Self-stigmatization also happens, wherein the patient stays away from the community members and sometimes from their families. 55% of non-compliant patients did not get family support for nutrition, transportation, or accompaniment to the center or encouragement. Given a choice, most patients would choose a family member to be their direct observer and preferred DOT at home to reduce stigma. This problem could be solved by keeping them properly informed about the actions of each medicine that they take, mode of transmission of this disease and by letting them join support groups. If a home-based DOTS is set up, educating and supporting people taking treatment should also be continuously done.

Health Care Facilities

The longer the travelling time, the more the patients would be non-compliant. 80% of the non-compliant patients were more likely to have longer traveling time. A considerable percentage of defaulters who claimed that swallowing many pills into an empty stomach after long waiting was awful.

Geo mapping the location of patients and clustering them with the nearby DOTS clinic would solve this issue. An SMS program that would further help by informing the patients on what cluster they belong and where the DOTS clinic assigned to them is located.

Health Care Services

In the past, significant relationship was also found between compliance and availability of DOT provider to every visit of DOTS clinic. Other studies also suggest that the poor relationship between the patients and the health-care providers also contributes to the non-compliance to DOTS. The team thinks that this could be solved by conducting regular trainings of DOT provider, stressing on the importance of establishing good relationship with the patients and, of course, this could also be a way for them to get the latest updates regarding TB.

As this program clearly addresses the different factors contributing to the non-compliance of TB patients to DOTS, it's geared towards providing better outcomes for TB patients and, consequently lessens the number of TB cases in many affected countries around the globe.

II. Market Analysis

A. Review of existing solutions to solve this problem

Non-mobile Solutions

New test, researchers led by Dr. David Alland, from UMDNJ, with Cepheid, developed a diagnostic DNA-based test called Xpert MTB/RIF which detects the TB-causing bacterium *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and also *M. tuberculosis* which is resistance to rifampin (RIF). This technology is essential because it can determine the difference between active & latent TB.

In Sub-Saharan Africa, some giant rats were trained to sniff out tuberculosis in humans. The results were pretty promising as those rats registered 92% correct detections of cultured bacteria.^[4]

Based from inexpensive lateral flow antibody test strip technology, a saliva or serum test was devised by Naval Dental Research Institute to detect exposure to tuberculosis and even give prognosis based on the efficacy of antibiotic treatment. ^[5]

Biomarker studies in the USA, Philippines and UK are ongoing, with initial results appearing to be promising.

[6] A point of care system based on the biomarker breath test which is non-invasive and is completed in 6 minutes was tested in the Philippines, UK and India showed a 98% negative predictive value and 13% positive

predictive value. [7]

Natural remedies are also said to be helpful to patients with tuberculosis. Herbal teas, garlic, astragalus, rhodiola and essential oils like eucalyptus and spearmint may not directly cure TB, but they address some of the signs and symptoms that the patient experiences. Some of those, specifically teas and garlic, may boost the immune system of a person infected with TB. [8]

Team's Ideas (Non-mobile Solutions)

1. Design a tablet that changes color to detect TB. Procedure is patient is administered the tablet and in 5 seconds, asked to spit it out. If the tablet color suppose white remains unchanged, he is not affected by TB, if it changes color to say pink, early stages and if it changes color to blue, need to sign up for treatment.
2. Design an inhaler kind of a device which is available for healthcare workers; it works like this, healthcare workers carry the inhaler kind of device to the homes, and the persons are asked to exhale into the device, the device has a series of LED indicators, white, pink, blue, as the LED glows, the healthcare worker can diagnose for TB bacteria.
3. Supply a strip to TB patients who are undergoing treatment at their home, where they can find out for themselves the improvement in their health because of taking the medication. This strip has a chart like indicator and based on the concentration of TB bacteria or lack of TB bacteria in the urine, it will glow a certain color or series of colors on the strip, and this will help the TB patient to indicate the level reduction in TB bacteria due to medication. This principle of working is similar to the strip used for testing diabetics / sugar content in urine

mHealth solutions

mHealth Alliance and the Stop TB Partnership has written a report in 2012 that notes down how mobile devices and softwares could help in fighting TB. It supported that an mHealth strategy could encourage patients to adhere to TB medication regimens by offering mobile credits or other incentives.[10]

In India, The Union, Eli Lilly and Dimagi collaborated to launch a mobile application (through Android-based mobile phones pre-loaded with Commcare) that targets to improve referral and case notification rates through the active involvement of rural health care providers (RHCPs) and lab technicians.[9]

Another Android-based application, eMocha, was launched in 2011 through the partnership between Johns Hopkins Centers for Clinical Global Health Education and TB Research. The primary function of this app is data collection and it could also seamlessly transfer those to a server where medical staff can access medical information.[11]

B. The Stakeholders

Patients with tuberculosis are the primary stakeholders of this program. They are the ones who will undergo it and also gain much of the expected outcome. Investors, health care providers, and suppliers of healthcare resources needed by these patients like pharmaceutical companies are also included in this equation towards

TB eradication.

III. Brainstorm solution options

To create a mobile application/ platform that has the following functions:

1. Recognition of symptoms and who to screen, addressing them in accordance to the referral system of DOTS wherein physicians and healthcare workers within the area refer to the DOTS clinic, if TB is suspected, and patients get free service (sputum examinations, cultures). Patients may be lost along the way so an mHealth solution on tracking patients, relay of results, a mobile general information campaign, or a step by step way of motivating the patient, ensuring him that he comes out the other end of the system TB free.

2. Diagnosed patients have an option to have self treatment (patient buys own medicine and administers it on their own) or enroll in a D.O.T.S. program with daily visits to ensure a directly observed taking of the medications. Two possible functions of this proposed mHealth app may come in for those options. Reminders are to be given to those self administering and an mHealth solution for monitoring both enrolled and self administering patients.

IV. Business Model

Patient, having heard about the probable signs and symptoms of TB on an information dissemination campaign or the like, either comes in a regular frontline clinic (A) or directly to a DOTS Clinic (B)

Patient seen at Clinic (A) and is considered to be a TB suspect would have his/her mobile number enrolled by Clinic (A). Clinic (B) would then have the mobile numbers of TB suspects.

Solution 1:

Clinic (A) sends TB suspect (X) mobile number to DOTS clinic (B) for enrollment.

DOTS Clinic (B) Receives mobile number of both Clinic (A) and TB suspect (X)

DOTS Clinic (B) sends daily SMS to TB Suspect (X) until he physically arrives at the DOTS clinic (5) wherein Dots Clinic (B) sends a feedback to Clinic (A) that TB suspect (X) was seen at the TB clinic.

Solution 2:

Patients (x) sent for sputum exam/culture at a laboratory will receive SMS from (B) as a reminder to bring/submit specimen until (C) sends feedback that (X) has completed the procedure.

Solution 3:

Laboratories (C) relay results to (B) wherein (B) informs (X) that results are available and that he/she should go to the nearest DOTS clinic, based on the geographical data supplied to the system.

Solution 4:

TB patients enrolled (Y) get daily reminders for their medications. Infotexts are also provided about potential side effects and other complications until they complete the course of treatment.

Solution 5:

Patient (X), (Y) who successfully completes (1), (2), (3) or (4) may send a coded reply to (B) which states accomplishment of task discontinuing the SMS.

Repetitive SMS from (B) may only be cancelled or unenrolled if (X) replies with a receive code from his/her intended destination or (Y) upon completion of treatment. --> Idea for automation

Campaign Strategy

Awareness Drive using Social Media:

This is how awareness will be built. An information dissemination campaign for TB Eradication may be done through the following: YouTube, TV, websites, Slideshare, (mobile) radio, and print media.

Admission Drive:

This is how patients will be enrolled to the mHealth program. We may utilize the following: existing list of enrolled patients, SMS Questionnaire leading to "contact me" and/or referrals, website questionnaire leading to "contact me" and/or referrals, inbound calls to clinics, DOTS clinics, grassroot healthcare workers, and list of patients identified with TB at health clinics

Evaluation:

This will give way to the improvement of the information dissemination process as we rethink about the strategy for awareness and admission drives' success. In this part, we will consider the following: Number of persons: contacted, qualified as TB patient, enrolled, successfully completed treatment, currently undergoing treatment, relapsed, consumption of medication, and word-of-mouth referrals.

Basic Interface / Layout

 Basic Interface

The combination of support coming from both the government and private sector would be pivotal for the success of this program. This will also be beneficial for both of these sectors.

GOVERNMENT SECTOR

 Government Sector

Since DOTS is a program funded by the government, (like how it is covered as an insurance package under PhilHealth, the national health insurance company of the Philippines) this mHealth program may potentially lessen the expenditure on this aforementioned course of treatment and the saved budget may be allocated to other of their prioritized health care programs.

PRIVATE SECTOR

 Private Sector

The private sector, on the other hand, including the service provider may be able to benefit from this program through the revenue it may gain from targeted advertisements and a market with increased number of subscribers.

Though there'll be a lot of work to be done at first, the cost of maintenance will gradually decrease and the development of this program will be a shared responsibility among all of the previously mentioned stakeholders.

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APPENDIX

A. Business Model Summary

<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Device Accelerators * Clinical Organizations * Government * NGO Foundation * Mobile Network Service Providers 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Awareness Campaign * Diagnosis * TB Control * Medication Administering * Case Study * Data Management * Training of Healthcare workers 	<p>Value Propositions</p> <p><u>To Patient</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Employable Certificate * SMS Credits * Referral Benefits * Compliance Benefits * Family enrollment for Free Healthcare Checkup 	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Patient Programs * Government Programs * NGO Programs * Mobile Network Service Providers * Healthcare Institutes 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Device Manufactures * Clinical Organizations * Healthcare Institutes * Mobile Network Service Provider * Health Insurance Agencies
	<p>Key Resources</p> <p><u>One-time Resources</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * TB Medication <p><u>Reusable Resources</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Diagnostic Devices * Mobile Phone * PC / Laptop * Training material <p><u>Periodic Resources</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Data warehouse * Server Application * Mobile Application * Device Interfacing Application * Web Maintenance 	<p><u>To Partners</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Non-invasive Trails Evaluation * Mobile Network Service Provider Loyalty Proposition <p><u>Globally</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Control and Prevention of Imported TB * Awareness of TB Zones 	<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Device Manufactures * Existing Clinics * DOTS Clinics * Government * NGO Foundation * Mobile Network Service Providers * Social Media – YouTube, Facebook, Web Advertisements, TV, Radio, Print Media * Word-of-mouth and Referrals 	
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Awareness Campaign using Paid Networks (SMS, TV, Radio, Print Media) * Procurement, Dispensing, Maintenance of TB Medication * Patient Care facility at Clinic * Patient Care facility at DOTS Clinic * Referral Benefits * SMS Credit expenses 		<p>Revenue Streams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Device Manufactures * Healthcare Private Sector * Government * NGO Foundation * Health Insurance Agencies * Mobile Network Service Provider 		

B. ABOUT THE TEAM

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